

REVISION OF THE COLLECTION OF THE GENUS *ASTRAGALUS* L. IN THE
HERBARIUM OF KOKAND STATE UNIVERSITY (KD)

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada Qo‘qon davlat universiteti Biologiya kafedrasida gerbariy fondida (KD) saqlanayotgan *Astragalus* L. turkumi tahlili yoritilgan. Tahlil natijalariga ko‘ra, *Astragalus* turkumining 11 turining jami 57 ta gerbariy namunalari saqlanayotganligi aniqlandi.

Kalit so‘z: *Astragalus ferganensis*, gerbariy, flora, O‘rta Osiyo, ekspeditsiya, Regel.

Аннотация: В статье представлен анализ рода *Astragalus* L., хранящегося в гербарном фонде кафедры биологии Кокандского государственного университета (KD). В результате анализа установлено, что хранится 57 гербарных образца 11 видов рода *Astragalus*.

Ключевое слово: *Astragalus ferganensis*, гербарий, флора, Средняя Азия, Ферганская долина.

Annotation: This article describes an analysis of the genus *Astragalus* L., which was stored in the herbarium fund of the Department of Biology of Kokand State University (KD). Analysis revealed that 57 herbarium specimens from 11 species of the genus *Astragalus* were stored.

Keyword: *Astragalus ferganensis*, herbarium, flora, Middle Asia, Ferghana valley.

Introduction. In recent years, targeted research has been conducted on certain families, genera, and species stored in various large herbarium collections worldwide, and inventories of herbarium collections have been conducted. Because of the inventories of certain families, genera, and species stored in the herbarium funds of the National Herbarium of Uzbekistan (TASH), the largest herbarium fund in Middle Asia, and Samarkand State University (SAMDU), research is being conducted on specimens stored in these herbarium funds, and the results have been published [3,4].

In 2024, the smallest herbarium fund in Uzbekistan was established at the Department of Biology (KD) of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, which contributed to the study of Uzbekistan and global biodiversity [8]. From 2024 to the present, analysis of the Fabaceae, Lamiaceae, and Boraginaceae families has been conducted in the KD herbarium fund. In particular, the herbarium fund contained 35 herbarium specimens belonging to 8 genera of the Lamiaceae family, 87 belonging to 13 genera of the Fabaceae family, and 116 belonging to 8 genera of the Boraginaceae family [6,7,8].

Figure 1. *Astragalus ferganensis* (Popov), B. Fedtsch. ex Korol. (Ferghana region, the surroundings of the village of Sarikurgan, Turdiboev, 09.05.2025)

Materials and methods. Herbariums stored in the KD fund are used in floristic research of specific regions and in the study of rare and endemic plant species [7]. Field research was conducted

from to 2024-2025 in Ferghana Valley. The works ‘Conspectus Florae Asiae Mediae’ (1981), ‘Flora of Uzbekistan’ (1961), and the taxon name databases POWO (2025) and IPNI (2025) were used to identify herbarium specimens [1,5,9,10].

Results and discussion. Establishing a herbarium fund for the Department of Biology (KD) of Kokand State University is an important step in the study of the flora of Uzbekistan. The newly established herbarium fund is considered important for the formation of the flora composition of the Ferghana Valley for the study of rare and endemic plant species. Herbarium specimens belonging to the genus *Astragalus* L. were stored in the herbarium fund (KD) of the Department of Biology of Kokand State University. As a result, 57 herbarium specimens belonging to 10 species of the genus *Astragalus* were stored (Table).

Table

Analysis of the *Astragalus* genus stored in the KD

№	Species	Number of herbariums
1	<i>Astragalus arpilobus</i> subsp. <i>arpilobus</i>	5
2	<i>Astragalus campylorhynchus</i> Fisch. & C.A. Mey.	7
3	<i>Astragalus ferganensis</i> (Popov) B.Fedtsch. ex Korol.	4
4	<i>Astragalus krauseanus</i> Regel	2
5	<i>Astragalus nematodes</i> Bunge ex Boiss.	8
6	<i>Astragalus ophiocarpus</i> Benth. ex Boiss.	3
7	<i>Astragalus orbiculatus</i> Ledeb.	12
8	<i>Astragalus rubellus</i> Gontsch.	4
9	<i>Astragalus stalinskyi</i> Širj.	2
10	<i>Astragalus</i> sp.	10
	<i>Jami:</i>	57

The most abundant herbarium specimen was *Astragalus orbiculatus* Ledeb. (12), *A. nematodes* Bunge ex Boiss. (8), *A. campylorhynchus* Fisch. & C.A. Mey. (7). The species with the fewest herbarium specimens in the fund was *Astragalus ferganensis* (Popov) B. Fedtsch. ex Korol. and *A. rubellus* Gontsch. It is a rare endemic species in the Ferghana Valley (Fig.1-2).

Conclusion. As a result of the analysis of herbarium specimens stored in the KD herbarium fund, it is necessary to enrich the herbarium specimens of rarely collected and uncollected species of the genus *Astragalus*. This is important for university students studying biodiversity and mastering botany science.

Figure 1. *Astragalus ophiocarpus* Benth. ex Boiss. (KD)

References

1. IPNI (2025). International Plant Names Index. Published on the Internet <http://www.ipni.org>, The Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, Harvard University Herbaria & Libraries and Australian National Herbarium. [Retrieved 12 May 2025].
2. Ismoilova R., Abdupattoyeva M., Usmonov S., Turdiboyev O. (2025) Analysis of the Boraginaceae family in the herbarium fund of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute (KD) // Kokand SPI. Scientific reports. Vol. 1. Pp. 167-170.

3. Madaminov F.M., Akbarov F.I., Turginov O.T., Tojibaev K.Sh. (2021). Analysis of the species in the genus *Parrya* R. Br., which is being kept in the unique scientific object National Herbarium of Uzbekistan (TASH) // Scientific Bulletin. №4(3), 10. Pp. 5-12.
4. Makhkamov T.Kh., Ibodullaeva Y.O. (2021). Revision of the collection of the genus *Corydalis* in the National Herbarium of Uzbekistan (TASH) // Systematic notes on the materials of the P. N. Krylov Herbarium of Tomsk State University. Vol. 123. – PP. 43-52.
5. POWO (2025). "Plants of the World Online. Facilitated by the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. Published online: <https://powo.science.kew.org/>Retrieved May 20, 2025."
6. Sobitjonova, F., Abdupattoyeva, M., Usmonov, S., Turdiboyev, O. (2025). Analysis of Fabaceae family in the herbarium fund of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute (KD) // Kokand SPI. Scientific reports. Vol. 1. Pp. 199-202.
7. Turdiboev O.A., Ruzimatov R. Taxonomic analysis of the flora of the Akbarabad natural monument // Spiraeanthus. 2024. Vol. 1. Pp. 109-111.
8. Tursunova, Sh. S., Raximjonova, Z. A., Sodiqov, S. S., Ismolilova, R., & Turdiboyev, O. (2024). Analysis of the Lamiaceae family in the herbarium fund of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute (KD) // Proceedings of Current Issues and Solutions in Natural Sciences. Pp. 6-8.
9. Vvedensky A.I. (Eds.) *Conspectus Florae Asiae Mediae*. 1981. Vol. 6. P. 394.
10. Vvedensky A.I. (Eds.) *Flora of Uzbekistan*. 1955. Vol. 3. P. 825.